

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING THE SUBJECT "TARBIYA" BASED ON INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article reveals the essence of inclusive education and the importance of its implementation in general education schools. The article discusses the psychological and pedagogical features and importance of teaching the subject "Tarbiya" based on the inclusive education method in primary education.

Key words: Inclusion, inclusive education, ability, individual, psychological competence, pedagogical approach.

Introduction:

The purpose of all the reforms carried out in our republic is to build a solid foundation for the future of our country. This foundation is created as a result of raising healthy, mature and mature individuals. That is why the "National Personnel Training Program" and the Law "On Education" were adopted. These reforms in the field of education are bearing fruit today. The scope of these legal regulations covers the education of children with special needs.

Currently, an inclusive education policy is being implemented in our Republic in order to ensure that children receive education in the special or general education system according to their development level, disabilities, and abilities.

Ideology of Inclusion Inclusion is a social concept. Inclusion in education is the stage of inclusion in society. The idea of an inclusive society is to transform society and its institutions in a way that promotes the acceptance and participation of all members of that society. Inclusion is recognized as a developed, humane and effective education system not only for children with special educational needs, but also for healthy children. Inclusion in education as a condition for inclusion in society Education of children with special needs is one of the main tasks before the country. This is a necessary condition for creating a truly inclusive society in which everyone can feel the participation and relevance of their actions.

Inclusive education is based on equality in the interaction between the teacher and the student. In this respect, inclusive education is characterized by providing equal education to students with physical and mental disabilities and students with full potential. On the initiative of the head of our state, the former "Kindly houses" were named educational institutions. For this reason, education in educational institutions is considered a form of inclusive education.

- special education of students with physical and mental disabilities;
- implementation of sensory education;
- equal provision of the right to education and training;

- special approach to training;
- Trainings are conducted by experienced teachers.

It is necessary to pay attention to the following features of inclusive education:

In the countries of the world, special attention is paid to inclusive education. In this regard, UNESCO appealed to the countries of the world in 1989, asking them to implement the education and upbringing of the individual through the means of inclusive education. Because the form of inclusive education allows the full realization of the individual's right to education and upbringing. For example, one of the main tasks of inclusive education is the special education of children with complete disabilities individually in the family.

In order to use the possibilities of inclusive education, the teacher must be active. Effectiveness of inclusive education is achieved on the basis of regularly assigning assignments to learners, writing assignments as much as possible, and monitoring the results of assignments. All this requires special training to use inclusive education opportunities.

Primary school teachers are recommended to study in depth the basics, methods and specific features of inclusive education through independent education. Because knowing the form of inclusive education is useful in applying the education policy of the state to everyone.

The subject of "Education" occupies an important place among the subjects of general secondary education. Therefore, in the teaching of this subject, it is necessary to rely on different forms of education. Inclusive education makes it possible to cover this subject to the young generation of the entire society. According to our approach, it is necessary to popularize the experiences of teachers of our country on inclusive education.

Education is a pedagogical process aimed at forming certain physical, mental, spiritual, moral and spiritual qualities in a person. Education is the most ancient and eternal value that ensures the humanity of a person. Without education, neither an individual nor a human society can exist. Because the values that ensure the existence of a person and society are passed from one generation to another only because of education.

In pedagogical literature, the term "education" is used in broad and narrow senses. In a broad sense, education means the sum of all influences, activities, actions and aspirations aimed at forming a human personality, ensuring his active participation in the production of society and social, cultural, educational life. In this understanding, education includes not only the educational work carried out in the family, school, children and youth organizations, but also the entire social system, its leading ideas and all types of art. Also, the concept of education in a broad sense includes education and information.

In a narrow sense, education means pedagogical activity aimed at the development of physical development of a person, worldview, spiritual and moral image and aesthetic taste. Family and educational institutions and public organizations carry out educational work. Education and information acquisition are not included in the concept of education in the narrow sense. But any upbringing exists only in close connection with education. Because, in the process of education and information acquisition, not only the knowledge of a person increases, but also the development of moral and spiritual qualities is accelerated.

Education is crucial in the life of any society and any country. A country that is not sufficiently involved in the education of the young generation, in general, members of the society, faces stagnation and crisis. After all, in order to grow and develop in any society, along with material and spiritual wealth, education also develops. The general characteristics of the theory of education are determined by the following:

- *theoretical foundations of education;*
- *education didactics;*
- *educational practice.*

These issues form the basis of the new science "Education" established in Uzbekistan as the basis of the theory of education. For this reason, the role, importance and practice of education in the society are sufficiently perceived by people. Future primary school teachers should be equipped with theoretical knowledge, professional skills and practical competencies in this regard.

Basics of "Tarbiya" science.

On the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in 2020, a new discipline of "Tarbiya" was developed for the first time in the history of the Uzbek "Tarbiya" science. In this regard, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 6, 2020 No. 422 "On measures to gradually implement the science of "Education" in general secondary educational institutions" was adopted, and this Resolution "Concept of the subject "Education" for students of general secondary educational institutions" was approved. According to the decision, the subject "Education" was established by adding the following subjects:

1. Educational subjects "*Etiquette*" and "*Feeling of the Motherland*" taught in primary grades;
2. "*Idea of National Independence and Spiritual Foundations*" and "*History of World Religions*" subjects taught in upper grades.

As a result, a new science was formed. The following are the methodological bases of this "Tarbiya" science:

- *normative documents related to education;*
- *foundations and sources of education;*
- *laws, methods and technologies of education;*
- *practical issues of education.*

It is these principles that form the basis of educational science. Future elementary school teachers should master these basics at the required level. Otherwise, their professional training in the methodology of this science will not be at the required level. Also, by the decision, the training of pedagogues in the field of "Education" has been launched starting from the 2021-2022 academic year.

According to the "Concept of the subject "Education" for students of general secondary educational institutions", the following are the general foundations of this subject:

- *legal grounds;*
- *organizational bases;*
- *scientific and methodical bases.*

In this case, the legal basis consists of regulatory and legal documents related to education, the organizational basis means the teaching of science at the level of demand in general education schools, including primary education, and the scientific-methodical basis means the methodology of the science. According to the decision, the following are the main principles of the science of "Education":

- priority of national and universal values;
- development of conscious patriotism;
- based on modern scientific research;

- openness and transparency;
- support and encourage initiatives in the field of education;
- compatibility and proportionality of activities of state bodies, non-governmental non-commercial organizations and private sector participating in the implementation of the policy in the field of education.

Primary school teachers are required to master these principles of science in depth. Therefore, in the process of higher pedagogical education, in educational activities and independent educational research, it is one of the urgent issues to master these principles, to have the skills to apply them in activities, and to acquire the competence to follow them in professional activities. For this, it is necessary for each student to work individually, to work actively in cooperation with teachers, and to study the expression of the principles of education in life. In this case, it is necessary to make reasonable use of the possibilities of educational institutions, the conditions of the educational process, and the practical efficiency of the activity. Each student's mastery of the principles, foundations and promising goals of this science is one of the foundations of professional training.

The feature of inclusive education that can be implemented quickly and in a short period of time expands its possibilities. Therefore, it is necessary to implement inclusive education for educational institutions today.

Basing on interactive educational technologies. In this regard, it is appropriate to teach the subject of "Education" as much as possible, to divide students into groups. It is recommended to use the following technologies:

- information and communication technologies (*multimedia, television, virtual communication and others*);
- computer technology (*lessons are taught using computers*);
- independent educational technology (*in which the student is given a task and attention is paid to the creative performance of the task*).

These interactive technologies allow targeted teaching of the subject "Tarbiya" in primary education.

- students are divided into groups as much as possible;
- topics are assigned to each group;
- assessment of completed tasks based on creative approach;
- monitor the education level of students in the group.

Differentiated teaching. It is appropriate to use this basis of inclusive education in the teaching of the subject "Education" in primary education as follows.

Individualized training. The form of individualized teaching in the subject of "Education" in primary education provides the following opportunities:

- work with each student individually;
- development of physical and mental abilities of each student;
- working separately with students with physical and mental disabilities;
- to control the education of every student at the same level.

Summary:

In primary education, it is urgent to provide targeted knowledge on the organization of the science of "Education" by means of inclusive education, to form it with new methods and technologies of education. Therefore, this article tried to solve this educational problem.

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